

INVESTIGATION INTO THE BLAST LOADING OF POLYMER COMPOSITE MATERIALS IN MARINE STRUCTURES

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1 General Introduction

This research relates to the in air and underwater blast tolerance of glass-fibre composite (GFRP) sandwich and laminate structures. This is to provide for procedures for monitoring the structural response of such materials during blast events. Air-blast loading of GFRP sandwich panels used high-speed photography, in conjunction with Digital Image Correlation (DIC), to monitor the deformation of these structures under shock loading. Failure mechanisms have been revealed by using DIC and confirmed in post-test sectioning. Underwater blast loading of similar sandwich materials used strain gauges to monitor the structural response to underwater shocks. The effect of the backing medium (air or water) of the target facing the shock has been identified during these studies. Mechanisms of failure have been established such as core crushing, skin/core cracking, delamination and fibre breakage. Strain gauge data confirmed the mechanisms for such damage. These studies were part of a research programme sponsored by the Office of Naval Research (ONR) to study blast loading of composite naval structures. The data shown gives full-scale experimental results to assist development of analytical and computational models. It also highlights the importance of support and boundary conditions with regards to blast resistant design.

2 Background

Several studies have investigated the deformation and response due to explosive blast and related high rate loading on plates. Neuberger et al. [1, 2] have highlighted several early studies, which classified failure modes of structures under impulse loading, from large inelastic deformation to tearing and shear failure at the supports. Abrate [3] has reviewed these effects in relation to impact and high rate loading of

composites. In addition, shock tubes have been employed for shock/blast simulation studies. Tekalur et al. [4-6] have experimentally studied the effect of blast loading using shock tubes and controlled explosion tube loading of E-glass fibre based composites and other materials. Results suggested that the E-glass fibre composite experienced progressive damage during high-rate loading of the same nature as described in Hoo Fatt and Palla [7], with progressive front face failure due to indentation followed by complete core collapse. These studies have been developed by the same research group to good effect, with many parameters being examined such as the distribution of blast energy during the impact process [8] and retention of integrity of sandwich structures due to blast loads [9].

Within the Imperial research group, the interest has been on concentrating on implementing Digital Image Correlation (DIC) to aid failure diagnosis. This is using optical non-contact techniques that trace full-field out-of-plane surface displacements and strain. This has been used successfully during a series of experimental programs such as: Four-point bend tests to understand better the damage modes in composite sandwich material (2D DIC) [10]; ballistic impact of sandwich material to reveal the variation of response across differing skin configurations (3D DIC) [11]; joint strength analyses under blast loading (3D DIC) [12] and various impact scenarios on metallic and polymer based materials. This paper describes the use of DIC and related techniques to full-scale air-blast loading of sandwich structures.

Underwater blast loading of fibre-reinforced polymer composites has also been studied. There are several difficulties when conducting instrumented underwater blast testing. The main problem is the increased severity of this blast case compared to air-blasts. When changing the medium in which the

shock travels from a gas to a liquid there is an increase of speed of sound resulting in a significant rise in pressures generated by a blast event. It is for these reasons that underwater shocks and their interaction with surrounding submerged structures are of particular interest to the naval and related industries.

This investigation aims to highlight the mechanisms of failure observed within commercially available naval materials and improve the understanding behind the sequence of events responsible for such damage. This is with the underlying aim of improving computational simulations and hence the design process for marine structures.

3 Experimental

Fig. 1: Example of visible blast effects from an air blast with detonation to formation of smoke cloud of combustion products.

Large-scale marine standard sandwich composite panels have been subject to both air and underwater blasts. All sandwich materials were provided by SP Gurit manufactured by P.E. Composites. A typical air blast and underwater blast are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 respectively.

Test methods have been established for each blast type. Various strain monitoring techniques were employed to qualify the damage observed during each blast scenario. These were 3D DIC for air blast and strain gauges for underwater blast studies.

Fig. 2: Example of visible surface blast effects produced by underwater blast with detonation to the venting of the gas bubble.

3.1 Air blast loading of sandwich composite panels

To record data for the failure processes, DIC has been performed during all loading stages in the air blast case. Pressure measurements were taken for each test recording the reflected and side-on pressure. The exposed panel dimensions were 1.5 m by 1.3 m with sandwich core thickness varying from 30 to 50 mm representative of full-scale marine structures. These were subject to blasts of 30 to 100 kg C4 charges at a range of stand-off distances from 16 to 8 m.

3.1 Underwater blast loading of sandwich composite panels

Strain gauges (six on the front and six on the rear of the panels) were used during the underwater blast loading to monitor the onset of damage observed in the composite sandwich panels. Underwater blasts were conducted on similar constructions of panels of 0.4 m x 0.3 m exposed target area. The aspect ratio of the panels was also chosen to keep the behaviour of the structure to that of a plate. The two different sized panels (from air-blast and underwater blast) were designed to have a comparable aspect ratio. The larger panels, used for the air-blast, were to represent near to full-scale naval superstructures. Smaller samples were required for the underwater blast experiments to allow for sufficient rigid edge restraint. This also assisted in the manoeuvrability of the rig during test set-up. The smaller targets kept within sensible bounds of the test facility in terms of the depth and breadth of the pond, the explosives used, desired maximum pressures and hence blast

parameters (suitable guidelines for such underwater test designs are outlined in [13]). During the underwater blasts, the panels were subject to blasts of 1.0 kg C4 charge at a range of stand-off distances from 1.0 to 1.4 m at a depth of 6 m.

4 Results

4.1 Air blast loading of sandwich composite panels

Fig. 3: DIC displacement & strain plots related to pressure/ out-of-plane displacement of the sandwich panel target for a 30 kg charge at 14 m stand-off. Exposed sandwich target area was 1.6 by 1.3 m and the core thickness was 40 mm.

One DIC analysis result is shown in Fig. 3. This result corresponds to a 30 kg charge at 14 m stand-off from a GFRP/SAN foam core target. The DIC analysis mapped the out-of-plane deformation of this target and major principal strain. Other blast analyses identified the onset of failure in the target and provided other related full-field data for FE model verification. The recent trials tested cores of

30-50 mm thick sandwich panels against peak shock pressures of 200 to 800 kPa (impulse 0.6 to 1.7 kPa s). The more intense blasts at small stand-off distances generated front-face skin damage and complete core shear failure.

4.2 Underwater blast loading of sandwich composite panels

Underwater blasts were conducted on similar sandwich panels. Peak shock pressures ranged from 35,000 to 41,000 kPa (impulse 2.9 to 4.2 kPa s). Secondary pulses resulted in peak pressures of 2,800 to 3,900 kPa (impulse 15 to 20 kPa s).

Fig. 4: Effect of backing medium for underwater blasts on sandwich panels. Data is shown for gauge positions 4-6: (a) water-backed sandwich panel with shock: 300 bar; (b) air-backed sandwich panel with shock: 430 bar; (c) diagrammatic representation of air-backed sandwich panel deformation showing signs of typical impulsive behaviour.

The targets in the two cases presented here had either air or water as a backing medium supporting the sandwich panel. The effect of the backing medium was significant causing excessive core crushing compared to that observed in the air backed panels. Similarly the degree of skin damage was seen to reduce when the panel was water backed, supported by the denser fluid medium. This observation was qualified by the reduced surface strain recordings.

To be expected, there was a significant difference in response of GFRP sandwich panels to air-blast (30 kg at 8 to 14 m) and underwater blast loading (1.0 kg at 1.0 to 1.4 m) due to the different pressure-time signatures: peak shock pressures of 200 to 800 kPa (6 ms duration) to 35,000 to 41,000 kPa (0.2 ms duration) as well as the secondary pressure pulses arising from the movements of the gas bubble. Damage mechanisms changed from front-face skin damage and core shear cracking for air blast to severe core crushing (up to 50 %) and skin fibre-breakage on both front and back faces for underwater blast.

5 Marine relevance

To further this research, experiments are being conducted to evaluate residual strength of the targets that have been subject to blast loading. A variety of sandwich constructions are being assessed along with a variety of blast parameters and boundary conditions.

This extensive study provides better for an comparisons between the relative benefits of the different composite types in varying test/environmental conditions. A summary of experimental data collected to date on blast testing is given in Reference [14].

Underwater blasts have been conducted on tubular structures (see Fig. 5 which shows an example of underwater blast on composite tubes with and without water within the tube).

Air-blasts are scheduled to be conducted on novel carbon fibre sandwich constructions in Summer 2011.

Fig. 5: Strain gauge data 1 kg C4 charge at 1.4 m stand-off at 6 m depth for 2 composite tubular laminate targets (40 x 44 mm made from 8H satin weave US 7781) filled with either air or water.

6 Conclusions

Experiments performed on fibre reinforced polymer composite materials have provided informative data relating to failure of such composite materials under different blast loading conditions. This is both for air and underwater blast. Continuing research studies are addressing particular points observed during the experiments e.g. the effect of different support conditions on the onset of failure. These processes are studied using finite element (FE) modelling incorporating fluid structure interactions (FSI) to reveal damage and failure mechanisms. Such information will allow for a constructive evaluation of the blast resistance, blast effects and residual strength of a variety of glass fibre and carbon fibre skin orientations and materials as part of developing a valuable design tool for design data.

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